

A Study on the Probable Existence of Potassium Indium Alum with Radioactive Nuclei. Part I

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Distribution study with Ga^{67} and Fe^{59} as guests and potassium chrome alum and potassium aluminium alum as hosts has revealed that the requisite guest ions are taken up by the host components through mixed crystal formation. The study has been extended from tracer level to finite concentration of the guest ions. Constancy of λ confirms the previous finding that alums are mixed crystals forming in all proportions. Verification of the heterogeneous distribution law in case of In^{114} as guest and potassium chrome alum as host has been shown both at tracer level and at finite concentration of indium. Constancy of the heterogeneous distribution factor (λ) provides a positive evidence that thus far unknown potassium indium alum does exist. The value of the partition λ (0.18) is an indication that the alum is highly soluble. Causes of failure in its isolation has been discussed. Radioactive indicator thus finds an application in predicting the existence of the interesting compound which is thus far unknown.

Of all the trivalent elements, which form alums, indium has the highest ionic radius. Ammonium, rubidium, and cesium alums of indium have been described in the literature. Any attempt towards isolation of potassium and sodium indium alum has resulted in the formation of $MIn(SO_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, where M stands for potassium or sodium ions. The failure in the isolation of potassium indium alum may be ascribed to the following factors:

- (1) $KIn(SO_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ may have a wide range of stability in contrast to so-called unknown indium alum, the range of stability of which may be very narrow or it may throughout exist as a metastable phase.
- (2) The unknown alum may be highly soluble.
- (3) Exact experimental conditions may be too much stringent for its isolation.
- (4) It is not feasible to use a large quantity of such a rare element for phase rule study in details without some positive hope about its probable existence.

Evidently, the application of radioactive nuclei may overcome many of the difficulties mentioned above. The main objective of this work therefore was to derive evidence on the existence of potassium indium alum through distribution study with In^{114} as a tracer and suitable potassium alum as a carrier. In order to derive additional support for our finding, investigation of this nature in known systems, where both guest and host elements form alums, has become the subject matter of our study.

EXPERIMENTAL

Amongst the known systems, distribution study with Ga^{67} , Fe^{59} as tracer and potassium chromium alum and potassium aluminium alum as hosts was undertaken. In investigating hitherto unknown potassium indium alum, In^{114} was taken as the guest and potassium chromium alum as the host component.

Ga^{67} , In^{114} , and Fe^{59} of high specific activity were supplied by Messrs. N. V. Philips-Duphar. Chromium and aluminium alums used were of AnalaR variety. Finite quantities of gallium and indium used were of spectrochemical purity.

In case, where $\text{KCr}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was taken as host, a fresh stock solution for each day was prepared. The stock solution was kept at about 10° . Acidity was maintained at 1N with respect to H_2SO_4 . Aliquot parts from the stock solution were taken in different beakers and a definite amount of tracer was added to each. Varying degrees of supersaturation were obtained by adding different quantities of ethanol, taking care that the total volume remained near about the same in all cases. Supersaturation was then broken by vigorous stirring. In some cases where high percentage of alum was precipitated, it so happened that separation of crystals started before the total amount of ethanol required for the purpose was added. In these few cases, the values of λ were, however, observed to remain constant. Temperature was kept always below 10° . In heterogeneous distribution study, the crystals were immediately separated and in homogeneous distribution, the crystals in contact with the mother liquor were shaken in a low temperature bath for about 24 hours before separation. The precipitate was washed with cold water containing the same amounts of acid and ethanol as were in the mother liquor and nearly the same temperature was maintained. The crystals were then dissolved in acidulated water, made to a definite volume, and aliquot portions were taken for estimation of chromium and activity measurements.

When potassium aluminium alum was used as the host component, fractions of alum were precipitated from solutions having different degrees of supersaturation and containing the requisite activity by vigorous stirring at 6° . Acidity was maintained at 1N with respect to sulphuric acid. After the supersaturation was completely broken down, a part of the mother liquor was pipetted out. It was then made to a definite volume and aliquot parts of it were taken for estimation of aluminium and counting measurements from which the extent of precipitation of the alum and the activity carried with it were computed.

Iron and chromium were estimated volumetrically and aluminium was determined gravimetrically in the usual way as Al_2O_3 . Activity in all these cases was measured by G. M. tubes meant for measuring liquids. The homogeneous distribution coefficient¹ (D) and the heterogeneous distribution coefficient² (λ) were calculated from the following expressions:

$$D = \left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}} \right)_{\text{solid}} / \left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}} \right)_{\text{solution}} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$\lambda = \log \left(\frac{\text{Initial tracer}}{\text{Tracer in solution}} \right) / \log \left(\frac{\text{Initial carrier}}{\text{Carrier in solution}} \right) \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

1. Henderson and Kraoak, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 738.

2. Doernert and Hoskins, *ibid.*, 1925, 47, 662.

TABLE I

*Coprecipitation of Ga⁶⁷ with KCr(SO₄)₂·12H₂O at 5° ± 0.5°.*Initial chromium conc. = 8.0×10^{-3} M. Acidity = $0.5N$ (H₂SO₄).

Conc. of gallium.	Chromium precipitated.	Gallium precipitated.	λ .
Tracer level (carrier-free)	50.03%	43.95%	0.790
	54.80	46.07	0.790
	62.07	54.05	0.809
	89.02	72.07	0.792
	80.76	75.30	0.803
	Average		
8.7×10^{-6} M	60.28	52.12	0.798
8.70×10^{-5}	56.30	40.37	0.820
8.70×10^{-4}	50.52	44.85	0.845
8.70×10^{-3}	58.87	54.39	0.883
	75.77	71.01	0.873
Average			0.878

N.B. KCr(SO₄)₂·12H₂O was precipitated with ethanol from chrome alum solution containing the guest ion and was immediately separated. Heterogeneous distribution factor (λ) remained constant.

TABLE II

*Coprecipitation of Ga⁶⁷ with KCr(SO₄)₂·12H₂O at 6° ± 0.5°.*Initial Chromium conc. = 8.0×10^{-3} M, Gallium conc. = tracer level (carrier-free).
Acidity = $0.5N$ (H₂SO₄).

Chromium precipitated.	Gallium precipitated.	D .
48.71%	16.68%	0.211
54.36	19.86	0.208
62.42	26.33	0.215
70.69	31.20	0.188
76.55	42.30	0.225
84.41	53.05	0.214
89.25	63.22	0.207
Average		0.201

N.B. KCr(SO₄)₂·12H₂O was precipitated with EtOH from chrome alum solutions containing Ga⁶⁷. The precipitate was shaken in contact with the mother liquor for about 24 hours. Homogeneous distribution coefficient D came out constant.

TABLE III

Coprecipitation of Ga⁶⁷ with KAl(SO₄)₂ · 12H₂O at 6° ± 0.5°.

Conc. of aluminium remaining in soln. = 2.0×10^{-1} M. Gallium conc. = tracer level.
Acidity = 0.5N (H₂SO₄).

Aluminium precipitated.	Gallium precipitated.	λ .
35.06%	25.84%	0.89
41.94	32.73	0.73
58.87	47.02	0.71
67.51	54.64	0.70
		Average 0.71

N.B. KAl(SO₄)₂ · 12H₂O was precipitated from supersaturated solution of the alum in dilute sulphuric acid containing tracer Ga⁶⁷ by vigorous stirring and the precipitate was immediately separated. Heterogeneous distribution factor (λ) came out constant.

TABLE IV

Coprecipitation of Fe⁵⁹ with KCr(SO₄)₂ · 12H₂O at 6° ± 0.5°.

Initial chromium conc. = 8.0×10^{-1} M. Acidity = 0.5N (H₂SO₄).

Conc. of iron.	Chromium precipitated.	Iron precipitated.	λ .
2.0×10^{-6} M	60.66%	13.90%	0.18
	64.04	15.02	0.16
	66.97	17.16	0.17
	67.19	16.21	0.16
	74.15	19.53	0.16
	83.66	25.89	0.16
	85.38	26.56	0.15
		Average 0.16	
8.0×10^{-6}	58.82	12.80	0.16
1.6×10^{-5}	57.49	12.90	0.16
8.0×10^{-4}	70.31	17.42	0.16
1.6×10^{-4}	67.20	16.94	0.16
8.9×10^{-4}	51.44	10.40	0.15
	68.16	10.20	0.16
	73.80	18.60	0.16
	84.50	26.30	0.18
	90.50	31.00	0.16
		Average 0.16	

N.B. Chrome alum was precipitated by vigorous stirring from ethanolic solution of the alum having different degrees of supersaturation with respect to the alum and containing the guest ion. The precipitate was immediately separated. λ values came out constant.

TABLE V

*Coprecipitation of In¹¹⁴ with KCr(SO₄)₂·12H₂O at 5° ± 0.5°.*Initial chromium concentration = 8.0×10^{-2} M. Acidity = 0.5N (H₂SO₄).

Concentration of indium.	Chromium precipitated.	Indium uptake.	λ .
4.39×10^{-6} M	53.76 %	12.78 %	0.177
	68.10	18.55	0.179
	70.80	18.82	0.169
	72.20	19.50	0.174
	75.00	19.80	0.180
	80.70	24.04	0.174
	86.20	28.67	0.187
		Average	0.171
4.16×10^{-5}	75.43	23.25	0.188
	78.03	24.25	0.183
	75.65	23.38	0.188
2.66×10^{-3}	04.08	17.15	0.179
	74.54	22.22	0.184
	77.38	23.52	0.188
	87.14	30.32	0.172
		Average	0.182

N.B. KCr(SO₄)₂·12H₂O was precipitated with EtOH from solutions containing the guest ion. The precipitate was then immediately separated. Heterogeneous distribution factor (λ) remained constant.

DISCUSSION

Ga⁶⁷ has been found to be a very suitable tracer because of the solubility of the corresponding alum in question to have a favourable partition factor. Uptake of Ga⁶⁷ by two host alums, namely potassium aluminium alum and potassium chrome alum, has been investigated. In case of the former, heterogeneous distribution has been studied (Table III). Both heterogeneous and homogeneous distribution factors have been studied with potassium chrome alum as host (Tables I and II). In case of Fe⁵⁹ as the guest and chrome alum as the host, only heterogeneous distribution factor has been studied (Table IV). It appears from these tables that wide variations as regards the fraction of the carrier precipitated occur in all these cases. Constancy of distribution factor, even in such large variations, is a positive proof that these are not accidental coincidences. In case of chrome alum as host and gallium and iron as guests, distribution factors have been studied from tracer concentration to finite concentration of the requisite guest ions. Tables I and IV show that the distribution factor remains constant though concentration of the guest ion varies from tracer level to finite concentration. The constancy of λ values throughout the entire range of concentration of the guest ions is a strong evidence that uptake takes place, as is expected, through mixed crystal formation. This study throws some light on the well-known fact that alums form mixed crystals in all proportions. Table II shows that D

values though constant are about one fourth of the λ values (Table I). This discrepancy may be due to the fact that λ values are susceptible to experimental conditions. This requires further investigations.

From the study of the above-mentioned known systems, it is evident that if in the coprecipitation of In^{114} with any potassium alum the uptake obeys either of the distribution laws (heterogeneous or homogeneous) in accordance with experimental conditions, it can be safely inferred that thus far unknown potassium indium alum may exist. Attempts were made to have wide variations in crystallising fractions of the host components. Constancy of distribution factor (λ), as is evident from Table V, indicates that In^{114} is taken up by the potassium chromium alum in question through mixed crystal formation. In consideration of the analogy of indium with chromium with reference to trivalent state in this type of system, conclusion can be arrived at that potassium indium alum does also exist. In order to obtain a thorough insight into the nature of uptake, we increased the concentration of indium in solution from $4.38 \times 10^{-6}M$ to $2.66 \times 10^{-3}M$ and measured the partition factor (Table V). At the highest concentration of the guest ion, constancy of λ has also been checked by crystallising different fractions of the host lattice. It is of interest to note that λ values remain near about the same throughout the entire range. It is therefore a case of true mixed crystal formation. Our finding on the existence of hitherto unknown potassium indium alum has therefore got sound justification.

It is of interest to point out that it would not have been easy to predict the existence of potassium indium alum without the application of radioactive indicators. Radioactive nuclei thus find an interesting application in this field of study.